

Studies on the Citrate Complex of Cobalt (II)

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The citrate complexes of Cobalt (II) has been studied by pH titration method within the pH range of 2.5 to 6.8. The results are confirmed qualitatively by measurement of specific conductance. Cobalt reacts with citric acid at lower pH forming a neutral complex C, liberating two protons simultaneously. The equilibrium constant of the reaction

is 8.40×10^{-5} . The neutral complex then dissociates at higher pH range in two steps to complexes C_1^- and C_2^{2-} . The equilibrium constants of the reactions, $\text{C} \rightleftharpoons \text{C}_1^- + \text{H}^+$ and $\text{C}_1^- \rightleftharpoons \text{C}_2^{2-} + \text{H}^+$, are 6.835×10^{-5} and 1.05×10^{-8} respectively. The formation constant of the complex C according to $\text{Co}^{2+} + \text{HCit}^{2-} \rightleftharpoons \text{C}$ is determined to be 1.439×10^3 . The equilibrium constant of the reaction

is determined to be 3.38×10^{-6} . The hydrolysis constant of the hydrolysis of Co^{2+} according to $\text{Co}^{2+} + \text{H}_2\text{O} \rightleftharpoons \text{CoOH}^+ + \text{H}^+$ is calculated to be 4.285×10^{-5} .

M. Bobtelsky and Heitner (*Bul. Soc. chim.*, 1951, 494) studied by spectrophotometric methods the effect of the addition of citrate and alkali to the citrate complexes of Ni, Co, Cu, Cr.

Tsimbler and Derenovskii (*Chem. Abst.* 1955, 49, 10787) on treatment of CoCl_2 with excess of a solution containing trisodium citrate and sodium hydroxide in equivalent ratios of 4:1 to 3:1 found that $\text{Na}_2(\text{CoC}_6\text{H}_4\text{O}_7)$ was formed and that the reaction of 4 equivalents of trisodium citrate with 1 of CoCl_2 yielded $\text{Na}_4\text{Co}(\text{C}_6\text{H}_4\text{O}_7)_2$. They also found that these complexes could be precipitated by methanol and not by ethanol. Thus in the presence of excess of NaOH, the OH and CoOH groups participate in complex formation, but in the absence of sodium hydroxide only the latter group reacts.

EXPERIMENTAL

Results of titrations of the solutions by pH and conductivity methods are recorded in Tables A and B respectively,

TABLE A

Exp. No.	Temp.	Vol.	Solution titrated	Content. (g. mol)	Conc. of the soln. used for titration.	Results.
I	$32.5 \pm 0.5^\circ$	130 e.o.	$\left\{ \begin{array}{l} \text{NaClO}_4 \\ \text{H}_3\text{Cit} \end{array} \right.$	0.025	NaOH 0.5M	Fig. 1 Curve A
				0.003		
		130	$\left\{ \begin{array}{l} \text{NaClO}_4 \\ \text{H}_3\text{Cit} \\ \text{CoCl}_2 \end{array} \right.$	0.025	-do-	Fig. 1 Curve B
	0.003					
	0.0025					
II	$32 \pm 0.5^\circ$	200	$\left\{ \begin{array}{l} \text{H}_3\text{Cit} \\ \text{CoCl}_2 \end{array} \right.$	0.025	NaOH 1M	Fig. 2 Curve A
				0.025		
		200	$\left\{ \begin{array}{l} \text{H}_3\text{Cit} \\ \text{CoCl}_2 \end{array} \right.$	0.025	-do-	Fig. 2 Curve B
				0.0025		

TABLE A (contd.)

Exp. No.	Temp.	Vol.	Content (g. mol)	Conc of the soln, used for titration	Results
III	33±0.5°	100	NaClO ₄ 0.025	Na ₂ HCit 0.1M	Fig. 3 Curve A
		100	{ NaClO ₄ 0.025 CoCl ₂ 0.00125	-do-	Fig. 3 Curve B
IV	32.5°±.5°	100	NaClO ₄ 0.025	Na ₃ Cit 0.1M	Fig. 4 Curve A
		100	{ NaClO ₄ 0.025 CoCl ₂ 0.00125	-do-	Fig. 4 Curve B
		120	{ Na ₃ Cit 0.01 NaClO ₄ 0.025	NaOH 0.1M	Fig. 5 Curve A
V	33°	120	{ Na ₃ Cit 0.01 NaClO ₄ 0.025 CoCl ₂ 0.001	-do-	Fig. 5 Curve B

TABLE B

VI	33±0.5°	250	H ₃ Cit 0.0003	NaOH 0.1M	{ Fig. 6 Curve A Fig. 6 Curve B
		250	{ H ₃ Cit 0.0003 CoCl ₂ 0.00025	NaOH 0.1M	
VII	33±0.5°	270	Conductivity water	Na ₃ Cit 0.1M	Fig. 7 Curve A
		270	CoCl ₂ 0.0001	Na ₃ Cit 0.1M	Fig. 7 Curve B

DISCUSSION

The *pH* of system (B) in each case is lower than the corresponding *pH* in system (A). As observed in the nickel citrate system, acid is therefore liberated due to complex formation. The horizontal distance between the two curves increases gradually up to *pH* 4.1, but then decreases with increasing *pH*.

In experiment II the ratio of the metal to ligand is 1:10. The horizontal distance between the two curves at first increases and remains very nearly constant within *pH* range 3.2 to 5.2. If the horizontal distance between the two curves is taken roughly as the measure of the amount of acid liberated (the concentration of citric acid is large compared to the concentration of this metal), it is found that only one equivalent of acid per atom of cobalt is liberated within the *pH* range 3.2. to 5.2. It is therefore very probable that the complex formed contains only one citrate ligand per atom of Co.

In experiment III (Fig. 3) the *pH* of the system containing no cobalt is nearly constant, even with increased amounts of two-third neutralised citric acid (HCit²⁻). The *pH* is lower in presence of cobalt, which is not only due to the removal of HCit²⁻ ions and formation of a complex but due to the dissociation of the complex as an acid. The complex formed by the HCit²⁻ ion with Co²⁺ is probably a stronger acid than HCit²⁻ ion.

In experiment IV B (Fig. 4) the *pH* decreases in the first instance with addition of increasing amounts of sodium citrate and then increases after the addition of just a little more than 1 g. mole of sodium citrate per g. atom of Co.

FIG. 1. Amount of 0.5M NaOH added in ml.

Calculation of the Equilibrium Constant

The reaction taking place in experiment I may be represented as before by

where C is the cobalt citrate complex (the charge of the complex, if any, is not mentioned). The equilibrium constant may be represented by

$$\frac{[\text{C}][\text{H}^+]^n}{[\text{Co}^{2+}][\text{H}_3\text{Cit}]} = K \dots\dots\dots(1-1)$$

FIG. 2. Amount of 1M NaOH added in ml.

It can be shown as in the study of cadmium citrate complex (Pattnaik and Pani; this *Journal* 1957, 34, 673) that

$$\frac{\Delta [\text{NaOH}] - \frac{a}{b} \Delta [\text{C}_t]}{[\text{C}]} = n - \frac{a}{b} \dots\dots\dots(2)^*$$

When the formation of the complex is complete, $[\text{C}] = [\text{CoCl}_2]$ and hence

$$\frac{\Delta [\text{NaOH}] - \frac{a}{b} \Delta [\text{C}_t]}{[\text{CoCl}_2]} = n - \frac{a}{b} \dots\dots\dots (3)$$

* In an earlier paper on the citrate complex of nickel, (this *Journal* 1957; 34, 819), the corresponding equation was printed wrongly as $n + (a/b)$.

FIG. 3. Amount 2/3 neutralised citric acid added in ml.

$\Delta [\text{NaOH}]$, $\Delta [\text{C}_t]$, $[\text{CoCl}_2]$ and $\frac{a}{b}$ are calculated at different pH values as determined before. Substituting these in equation (3) a series of values of n , obtained at different pHs, are recorded in the Table I. Assuming n to be 2 below pH 3.7, the equilibrium constant of the reaction (1) is calculated according to the equation (1-1), as determined in the study of nickel citrate complex, and recorded in Table I. The mean value of K is 8.398×10^{-5} .

Towards higher pH range n is more than 2. The complex C dissociates like an acid with increasing pH

$$\frac{[C_1^-][H^+]}{[C]} = K_1 \dots\dots\dots(4-1)$$

It can be shown, as done in the case of cadmium citrate complex, that

$$K_1 = \frac{(n-2)[H^+]}{(3-n)} \dots\dots\dots(4-2)$$

FIG. 4. Amount of 0.1M Sodium citrate added in ml.

The values of the equilibrium constant K_1 , calculated by the above equation, are recorded in Table II. The mean value K_1 is found to be 6.835×10^{-5} .

TABLE I

pH.	Δ [NaOH]	Δ [Ct.].	a/b	n .	[C]	[Co ²⁺]	[H ₃ Ct.].	$K_1 \times 10^5$.
2.5	0.004485	0.00020	0.2131	0.4531	0.002534	0.01834	0.01589	9.761
2.6	0.00555	0.00026	0.2560	0.5545	0.003218	0.01560	0.01443	9.018
2.7	0.00660	0.00030	0.3046	0.6621	0.003948	0.01477	0.01293	8.228
2.8	0.00726	0.00033	0.3588	0.7554	0.004498	0.01412	0.01154	6.934
2.9	0.00898	0.00040	0.4184	0.9127	0.005776	0.01272	0.00971	7.411
3.0	0.01032	0.00047	0.4822	1.0563	0.006949	0.01104	0.00894	7.598
3.1	0.01197	0.00056	0.5499	1.2331	0.008468	0.00977	0.00835	8.614
3.2	0.01323	0.00061	0.6197	1.3706	0.009854	0.00827	0.00492	9.649
3.8	0.01918	0.00091	1.052	2.2000				
3.9	0.01966	0.00092	1.127	2.3130				
4.0	0.01955	0.00090	1.204	2.390				
4.1	0.01907	0.00089	1.282	2.447				
4.2	0.01897	0.00088	1.362	2.528				
4.3	0.01856	0.00085	1.445	2.592				
4.4	0.01811	0.00084	1.530	2.657				
4.5	0.01739	0.00080	1.615	2.723				
4.8	0.01527	0.00071	1.876	2.8474				

TABLE II

pH.	(n-2).	(3-n).	$K_1 \times 10^5$.
3.8	0.200	0.800	3.962
3.9	0.313	0.687	5.735
4.0	0.390	0.610	6.395
4.1	0.447	0.553	6.421
4.2	0.528	0.472	7.058
4.3	0.592	0.408	7.271
4.4	0.657	0.343	7.628
4.5	0.723	0.277	8.252
4.8	0.847	0.1526	8.802

In experiment III increasing amounts of 2/3 neutralised citric acid was added to a definite amount of cobalt chloride. It is assumed that 2/3 neutralised citric acid contains mostly HCit^{2-} ion. The reaction may be represented as

The equilibrium constant can be represented as

$$\frac{[\text{C}]}{[\text{HCit}^{2-}][\text{Co}^{2+}]} = K_3 \quad \dots\dots\dots(5-1)$$

The complex C being a stronger acid than HCit^{2-} (dissociation constant of C is 6.835×10^{-3} and that of HCit^{2-} is 3.24×10^{-6}) a part of the complex dissociates into C_1^- and H^+ by reaction (4). As sufficient HCit^{2-} is introduced, the formation of the complex C is complete and dissociation of C to C_1^- and H^+ continues with increasing addition of 2/3 neutralised citric acid. The equilibrium constant K_3 and dissociation constant K_1 of reaction (4) can be calculated from the results of experiment III. K_3 differs from K by a constant and it can be shown that

$$\frac{K}{k_1 k_2} = K_3 \quad \dots\dots\dots(5-2)$$

In the previous experiment the formation of the complex C was complete at pH 3.70. The pH in this system is always above pH 3.65. Hence it is expected that above pH 3.70, the formation of the complex C will be complete. Some cobalt ion will be present when the proportion of cobalt to citrate in the solution is greater than 1.

$$\text{Total cobalt} = [\text{CoCl}_2] = [\text{C}] + [\text{C}_1^-] + [\text{Co}^{2+}]$$

When the formation of the complex is complete,

$$[\text{Co}^{2+}] \text{ is very small and } [\text{CoCl}_2] = [\text{C}] + [\text{C}_1^-].$$

It can be shown (Pattnaik and Pani, this *Journal*, 1957, 34, 619) that

$$[\text{HCit}^{2-}] = \frac{[\text{C}_1^-] - [\text{CoCl}_2]}{x} \quad \dots\dots\dots(6)$$

and

$$[\text{C}_1^-] = [\text{C}_1^-] - [\text{CoCl}_2] \times (2 - \frac{y}{x}) + [\text{H}^+] \quad \dots\dots\dots(7)$$

where

$$x = 1 + \frac{[\text{H}^+]}{k_2} + \frac{K_3}{[\text{H}^+]}$$

$$y = 2 + \frac{[\text{H}^+]}{k_2} + \frac{3k_3}{[\text{H}^+]}$$

$[\text{H}^+]$ is obtained from Curve B in Fig. 2 and x and y are calculated. $[\text{C}_t]$ and $[\text{CoCl}_2]$ can be calculated from the g. moles of 2/3 neutralised citric acid added or g. moles of cobalt chloride taken and total volume of solution. $[\text{C}]$ is obtained by subtracting $[\text{C}_i^-]$ from $[\text{CoCl}_2]$ and K_1 is calculated by equation (4-1). The values are shown in Table III. The mean value of K_1 is 1.718×10^{-4} . This agrees fairly well with the value 0.684×10^{-4} obtained from the first experiment.

TABLE III

pH.	$[\text{C}_t]$	$[\text{CoCl}_2]$	y/x	$[\text{C}_i^-]$	$[\text{C}]$	$K_1 \times 10^4$
3.85	0.01611	0.01049	1.232	0.004457	0.00603	1.044
3.90	0.01729	0.01034	1.256	0.005207	0.00505	1.320
3.95	0.01895	0.01013	1.279	0.006470	0.00366	1.984
4.00	0.02013	0.009984	1.305	0.007153	0.002831	2.526
4.05	0.02212	0.009734	1.332	0.008366	0.001368	5.451

In the range in which proportion of cobalt to citrate is less than 1, Co^{2+} , C, and C_i^- exist. $[\text{C}]$ can be calculated by equation (4-1) at different pH, substituting the value of K_1 and $[\text{C}_i^-]$. $[\text{C}_i^{2-}]$ can be calculated as determined in the investigation of citrate complex of nickel (*loc. cit.*)

It can be shown that

$$[\text{C}_i^-] = \frac{[\text{C}_t] (2 - \frac{y}{x}) + [\text{H}^+]}{(3 - \frac{y}{x}) + \frac{[\text{H}^+]}{K_1} (2 - \frac{y}{x})} \dots\dots\dots (8)$$

and

$$2 [\text{C}_t] + [\text{H}^+] = [\text{C}_i^-] (3 + \frac{2 [\text{H}^+]}{k_1}) + y [\text{HCit}^{2-}] \dots\dots\dots (9)$$

$[\text{C}_i^-]$ and $[\text{HCit}^{2-}]$ are calculated by equations (8) and (9) respectively. $[\text{Co}^{2+}]$ can be obtained by subtracting ($[\text{C}] + [\text{C}_i^-]$) from $[\text{CoCl}_2]$. The values of K_3 are calculated and tabulated in Table IV. The mean value of K_3 is 1.4386×10^3 .

The values of K calculated from the corresponding values of K_3 according to equation (5-2) are in agreement with those calculated from the results of experiment I. The values are recorded in Table IV. The mean value of K is 4.585×10^{-5} . The value obtained before is 9.4×10^{-5} .

The results obtained in experiment IV are interesting. The pH of the system containing no cobalt (Curve A, Fig. 4) increases very rapidly at the beginning with increasing concentration of sodium citrate till pH 7.5 is reached. After this the increase in pH is gradual. In the other system containing cobalt chloride (Curve B), the pH falls very rapidly at the beginning, remains very nearly constant, and then increases rapidly till a little more than 1 g. mole of sodium citrate per g. atom of cobalt (II) is added. This is indicated by the break in the curve at P. After the inflexion point P, the rise in pH is

comparatively slow. The reaction of cobalt ion with citrate ligand at the beginning results in the liberation of a proton. The reaction therefore can be represented by

$$\frac{[\text{C}_2^{2-}] [\text{H}^+]}{[\text{Co}^{2+}] \times [\text{Cit}^{3-}]} = K_4 \quad \dots\dots\dots(10-1)$$

The above reaction alone cannot explain the results. Hence another reaction which removes the protons liberated by the above reaction probably takes place. Citrate ion has a strong basic property and as such is capable of removing protons. But most of the citrate added would be removed by cobalt for the formation of the complex. Hence very little free citrate would be available for the removal of protons till the complex formation is complete. It is therefore assumed that C_2^{2-} formed is converted into C_1^- by the following reaction as the pH is lowered.

$$\frac{[\text{C}_2^{2-}] \times [\text{H}^+]}{[\text{C}_1^-]} = K_2 \quad \dots\dots\dots(11-1)$$

This means that as the pH is lowered, the complex C_1^- is formed rather than the complex C_2^{2-} . The reaction may be represented by

Due to formation of C_1^- there would be no change in pH. Hence, when the pH is sufficiently lowered due to the formation of C_2^{2-} , further increase in the concentration of C_2^{2-} does not take place, but the concentration of C_1^- increases with increasing addition of sodium citrate and the pH remains very nearly constant. As the amount of sodium citrate added increases, the concentration of free citrate in the solution increases and as such the pH of the solution increases till the formation of the complex is complete (at P). As the pH rises up to the minimum and then remains very nearly constant, the dissociation of C_1^- to C_2^{2-} and H^+ ion also takes place besides the formation of the complex. At P the formation of the complex is complete. Above P due to rise of pH on addition of sodium citrate, reaction (11) proceeds in the reverse direction. Above the point P, the concentration of Co^{2+} would be very small and may be neglected. Hence

$$[\text{CoCl}_2] = [\text{C}_1^-] + [\text{C}_2^{2-}]$$

$[\text{C}_t]$ = total citrate = free citrate + citrate in complex

Citrate in complex = $[\text{C}_1^-] + [\text{C}_2^{2-}] = [\text{CoCl}_2]$.

Hence free citrate = $[\text{C}_t] - [\text{CoCl}_2]$.

But free citrate = $[\text{Cit}^{3-}] + [\text{HCit}^{2-}] + [\text{H}_2\text{Cit}^-] + [\text{H}_3\text{Cit}]$

As the pH is high, the concentration of $[\text{H}_3\text{Cit}]$ can be neglected.

Hence,

$$\begin{aligned} [\text{C}_t] - [\text{CoCl}_2] &= [\text{HCit}^{2-}] \frac{k_3}{[\text{H}^+]} + [\text{HCit}^{2-}] + [\text{HCit}^{2-}] \frac{[\text{H}^+]}{k_2} \\ &= [\text{HCit}^{2-}] \left\{ 1 + \frac{k_3}{[\text{H}^+]} + \frac{[\text{H}^+]}{k_2} \right\} \\ [\text{C}_t] - [\text{CoCl}_2] &= Z [\text{HCit}^{2-}] \quad \dots\dots\dots(13) \end{aligned}$$

$$\text{where } Z = 1 + \frac{k_3}{[H^+]} + \frac{[H^+]}{k_2}$$

$[HCit^{2-}]$ can be calculated from above equation (13)

$$\begin{aligned} \text{Total proton liberated} &= [C_2^{2-}] \\ &= [HCit^{2-}] + 2 [H_2Cit^-] + [H^+] \end{aligned}$$

$$\text{Or } [C_2^{2-}] = [HCit^{2-}] \times \left(1 + 2 \frac{[H^+]}{k_2}\right) + [H^+]$$

$$\text{Or } [C_2^{2-}] = r [HCit^{2-}] + [H^+] \dots\dots(14)$$

$$\text{where } r = 1 + 2 \left\{ \frac{[H^+]}{k_2} \right\}$$

$[C_1^-]$ is obtained by subtracting $[C_2^{2-}]$ from $[CoCl_2]$. Values of K_2 calculated by the equation (11-1), are recorded in Table V. The mean value of K_2 is 1.05×10^{-8} .

TABLE V

pH	$[C_1]$	$(CoCl_2)$	z	$[HCit^-]$	r	$[C_2^{2-}]$	$[C_1^-]$	$K_2 \times 10^8$
6.40	0.01319	0.01085	9.1467	0.0002559	1.01956	0.0002611	0.01059	0.9817
6.45	0.01402	0.01075	10.1397	0.0003225	1.01743	0.0003282	0.01042	1.1180
6.50	0.01489	0.01064	11.2477	0.0003781	1.0155	0.0003840	0.01026	1.183
6.55	0.01582	0.01052	12.4969	0.0004243	1.0138	0.0004305	0.01009	1.203
6.60	0.01681	0.01040	13.9062	0.0004613	1.01234	0.0004670	0.00994	1.180
6.65	0.01776	0.01028	15.4755	0.0004935	1.0110	0.0004891	0.00980	1.118
6.70	0.01883	0.01015	17.2449	0.0005035	1.00981	0.0005081	0.00964	1.052
6.75	0.02000	0.0100	19.2243	0.0005200	1.00874	0.0005243	0.00948	0.983
6.80	0.02113	0.00983	21.4438	0.0005257	1.00778	0.0005294	0.00933	0.899

Below the point P in Curve B (Fig. 4) the formation of the complex is not complete. Cobalt ion would be present besides the complexes C_1^- and C_2^{2-} .

$$\text{Total citrate } = [C_1] = [H_2Cit^-] + [HCit^{2-}] + [Cit^{3-}] + [C_1^-] + [C_2^{2-}]$$

By substituting the value of $[C_1^-]$ from equation (11-1)

we get

$$\begin{aligned} [C_1] &= [HCit^{2-}] \left(1 + \frac{[H^+]}{k_2} + \frac{k_3}{[H^+]}\right) + [C_2^{2-}] \left\{1 + \frac{[H^+]}{K_2}\right\} \\ &= p [HCit^{2-}] + q [C_2^{2-}] \dots\dots\dots (15) \end{aligned}$$

$$\text{where } p = 1 + \frac{[H^+]}{k_2} + \frac{k_3}{[H^+]}$$

$$\text{and } q = 1 + \frac{[H^+]}{K_2}$$

Substituting the value of (C_2^{2-}) from equation (14)

one gets

$$[C_t] = p [HCit^{2-}] + q [H^+] + qr [HCit^{2-}]$$

Or

$$[C_t] = q [H^+] + [HCit^{2-}] (p + qr) \dots\dots\dots(16)$$

r, p and q are calculated at different pH values and $[HCit^{2-}]$ can be calculated by equation (16). $[C_2^{2-}]$ is calculated by the equation (14). Substituting the value of $[HCit^{2-}]$ obtained above $[C_1^-]$ is calculated by equation (11-1). Co^{2+} is obtained by subtracting the $([C_1^-] + [C_2^{2-}])$ from $(CoCl_2)$. The concentration of free citrate ion (Cit^{3-}) can be calculated by the equation (15), by subtracting

$$([H_2Cit^-] + [HCit^{2-}] + [C_1^-] + [C_2^{2-}]) \text{ from } [C_t].$$

The equilibrium constant K_4 is calculated by equation (10-1) and the values are recorded in Table VI. The mean value is found to be 3.38×10^{-6} .

It can be shown that

$$\frac{K_4 \times k_1 k_2 k_3}{K_2 K_1} = \frac{[C] [H^+]^2}{[Co^{++}] [H_3Cit]} = K.$$

So it is expected that K would be equal to

$$\frac{K_4 \times k_1 k_2 k_3}{K_2 K_1}$$

The mean value of K and $\frac{K_4 \times k_1 k_2 k_3}{K_1 K_2}$ is 8.398×10^{-5} and 5.157×10^{-7} respectively.

Hence both the values are not equal. The low value of $K_4 k_1 k_2 k_3 / (K_1 \times K_2)$ may be due to the low value of K_4 caused by hydrolysis of Co^{2+} to $CoOH^+$ according to equation (17). This type of hydrolysis may occur to an appreciable extent at higher pH . K_4 is determined at pH 6.8, while K is determined at pH below 3.3.

The hydrolysis constant K_h of the reaction may be represented by equation (17.1).

$$K_h = \frac{[CoOH^+] [H^+]}{[Co^{++}]} \dots\dots\dots(17-1).$$

Calculation of Hydrolysis Constant

Cobalt (II) ions are partially hydrolysable. Hence the free cobalt assumed to be present as Co^{2+} ion in the determination of K_4 in experiment, IV would be less. The value of K_4 would therefore be more. It is assumed that the hydrolysis of Co^{2+} below pH 3.3 is negligible. The concentration of Co^{2+} ion in experiment IV would be such that

$$\frac{K_4 k_1 k_2 k_3}{K_1 K_2} \text{ would be equal to } K.$$

$$\text{Hence } [\text{Co}] = \frac{K}{\frac{K_4 k_1 k_2 k_3}{K_1 K_2}} \times [\text{Co}^{2+}]$$

$[\text{Co}]$ = free cobalt = conc. of Co^{2+} ion determined in experiment. IV.

$$\text{or } [\text{Co}^{2+}] = \frac{[\text{Co}] \times K_4 k_1 k_2 k_3}{K K_1 K_2}$$

$[\text{Co}^{2+}]$ is calculated by using the concentration of free cobalt shown in Table VII.

TABLE VII

pH.	$[\text{Co}]$.	$([\text{Co}^{2+}] \times 10^5)$.	$[\text{CoOH}^+]$	$K_h \times 10^5$.
6.8	.01223	7.504	0.01215	2.566
6.7	.01184	7.271	0.01177	3.229
6.6	.01128	6.926	0.01121	4.065
6.5	.01089	6.686	0.01083	5.122

$[\text{CoOH}^+]$ is obtained by subtracting $[\text{Co}^{2+}]$ from $[\text{Co}]$.

The hydrolysis constant, calculated by the reaction (17-1), is shown in Table VII and the mean value of K_h is 4.285×10^{-5} .

In experiment V (Fig. 5) curve B is very similar to the neutralisation curve of a strong acid. Incidentally, the neutralisation point is reached at about 11 c.c. of 0.1N alkali. The pH attained by the solution (system B), containing cobalt (II) due to the addition of 11 c.c. of alkali is reached by the other solution by adding 1 c.c. of the same alkali. Hence 10 c.c. of the alkali i.e., 0.001 g. mole of NaOH is consumed by the complex formed from 0.001 g. mole of cobalt chloride. The liberation of one proton per atom of cobalt indicates the formation of the complex C_2^{2-} .

FIG. 5. Amount of 1.0N NaOH added in ml.

In experiment VI (Fig. 6) curve A represents the neutralisation of citric acid. The specific conductance decreases at the beginning, comes to a minimum at about 30% neutralisation of citric acid, then increases gradually till the acid is completely neutralised, and then the conductance rises more rapidly.

Curve B represents the results obtained by neutralisation of citric acid in presence of cobalt (II). In this case also the conductance decreases till nearly 45% of the acid is neutralised. This is followed by a break at point P_1 . Then the conductance remains nearly constant up to the break at P_2 till 85% of the acid is neutralised. The conductance then rises slowly with the addition of sodium hydroxide. This continues up to the break at the point P_3 after which the conductance rises rapidly.

The conductance decreases rapidly in the beginning due to neutralisation of nitric acid and formation of the neutral complex C, which does not contribute to the conductance

FIG. 6. Amount of N/10 NaOH added in ml.

FIG. 7. M/10 sod. cit. added in ml.

TABLE IV

pH.	$[Cl^-] \times 10^3$.	$[CoCl_2] \times 10^3$.	η/sp .	$[C_1^-] \times 10^4$.	$[C] \times 10^4$.	$[Co^{+2}]$.	$[HCl^{+2}] \times 10^5$.	$K_4 \times 10^{-3}$.	$K \times 10^5$.
3.80	1.186	1.235	1.212	3.988	4.818	.01147	6.213	0.676	2.290
3.75	1.676	1.230	1.192	4.990	6.776	.01113	7.409	0.825	2.794
3.70	1.961	1.226	1.174	5.900	8.974	.01078	7.998	1.014	3.525
3.65	2.534	1.218	1.158	7.191	12.29	.01024	9.011	1.331	4.508
3.62	3.847	1.201	1.149	10.31	18.86	.00909	13.49	1.538	5.207
3.64	5.662	1.180	1.155	15.08	26.32	.00766	23.08	1.489	5.043
3.66	7.408	1.157	1.161	19.87	33.14	.00627	32.90	1.607	5.442
3.68	9.090	1.136	1.168	24.61	39.20	.00498	43.86	1.795	6.077
3.72	10.72	1.116	1.181	29.82	43.30	.00385	59.71	1.883	6.377

TABLE VI

pH.	$[Cl^-] \times 10^3$	$[CoCl_2]$	η .	τ .	ρ .	η .	$[C_1^-] \times 10^3$	$[Co^{+2}] \times 10^5$	$[Cl^{+2}] \times 10^4$	$K_4 \times 10^5$
6.70	0.990	.01238	17.2449	1.0098	19.59	2.638	0.5088	1.184	4.28	1.056
6.65	1.380	.01233	15.4755	1.0110	22.26	3.621	0.7630	1.151	5.24	1.368
6.60	1.675	.01230	13.9362	1.0123	24.85	4.015	0.9754	1.128	5.19	1.754
6.55	1.768	.01228	12.4969	1.0138	27.77	4.333	1.183	1.105	4.98	2.264
6.50	1.865	.01227	11.2477	1.0155	31.03	4.343	1.134	1.089	4.44	2.904
6.46	2.152	.01223	10.1397	1.0174	34.70	4.710	1.626	1.056	4.31	3.761
6.40	2.439	.01220	9.1467	1.0195	39.81	4.974	1.931	1.022	4.08	4.874
6.35	2.724	.01216	8.2929	1.0219	43.42	5.140	2.246	0.986	3.74	6.410

of the solution. After the first break at P_1 , formation of the complex C continues and the conductance remains very nearly constant. The conductance then gradually rises most probably due to the formation of C_2^- , which is nearly complete at the second break at P_2 . The conductance then rises more rapidly due to the formation of the complex C_3^{2-} , which is nearly complete at the third break at P_3 due to the increasing concentration of NaOH.

In the experiment VII (Fig. 7) the curves are exactly similar to those obtained in case of the nickel citrate complex (*loc. cit.*).

The conductance of the system containing cobalt (Curve B) is more than the system which does not contain cobalt up to the addition of one g. mole of sodium citrate per g. atom of cobalt.

After addition of 1 g. mole of sodium citrate per g. atom of cobalt, the conductance of the system containing cobalt becomes less than that of the system without cobalt and the difference of conductance between the curves becomes negligible and they run parallel to each other. This also supports that the complex formed contains one citrate ligand per atom of cobalt.

The structure of the cobalt citrate complexes is similar to those of the cadmium citrate and nickel citrate complexes (Pattnaik and Pani, *loc. cit.*).

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